

Table 4: Effect of Meal, energy, and nutrient distribution in a day on glycemic control in individuals at high risk for developing or with type 2 diabetes

Study	Age (years) BMI (kg/m ²) Health status	Duration and design of dietary intervention	Sample size	Description of groups	Dietary intervention	Selected clinical outcomes
<p>• Effect of the Number of meals per day on Glycemia</p>						
Papakons tantinou, et al., 2018 [175]	2 IGT groups (early and advanced stage) and T2D 49.3±1.8 32.4±0.8	24 weeks Randomized, crossover study	47	IGT-A (PG 140–199 mg/dL at 120 min post OGTT) IGT-B (PG levels 140–199 mg/dL at 120 min and >200 mg/dL at 30, 60 or 90 min post-OGTT) T2D (newly diagnosed treatment-naive T2D)	Weight maintenance diet: 1900kcal/day, 45% CHO, 20% PRO, 35% FAT 6 meals/ day (B, L, D, and 3 snacks; with CHO: 20% at B, 10% morning snack, 30% at L, 10% at afternoon snack, 20% at D and 10% at bedtime snack) Or 3 meals/ day (B, L, and D; with CHO: 20% at B, 50% at L and 30% at D) 12 weeks per regiment and then crossover to other regiment for 12 weeks	<u>T2D group:</u> ↓↓ post-OGTT Glu and ↓↓ HbA1c with 6 meals <u>IGT-A group:</u> ↓ 30-min and ↓↓ 60-min post- OGTT plasma Ins with 6 meals <u>IGT-B group:</u> ↓ peak Glu with 3 meals ↓↓ peak Glu with 6 meals <u>In all groups:</u> ↓ subjective hunger with 6 meals no differences in satiety or lipids no differences in FPG, Glu or Ins iAUC, fasting Ins, HOMA-IR with 3 vs 6 meals
Jakubowi cz et al., 2019 [177]	T2D ≥25 years 32.4±5.2 HbA1c: 8.1±1.1%	3 months Randomized, parallel, treated with insulin,	28	6 meals 3 meals	Isoenergetic diets consisting of 3 or 6 meals/day: 3M 700 kcal breakfast, 600 kcal lunch, 200 kcal dinner; 6M same as 3M and addition of 150 kcal snacks	12 weeks with 3meals/day vs 6meals/day -5.4 kg weight loss, - 1.2% total insulin dose – 26 units, higher clock gene expression

	T2D for ≥ 5 yrs, treated with insulin ≥ 1 yr with >25 units for at least 3 months	continuous glucose monitoring				
Kahleova, et al., 2014 [178]	T2D 59.4 \pm 7.0 32.6 \pm 4.9	24 weeks each regiment Randomised, open, crossover study	54	A6 regiment (6 meals/ day) B2 regiment (2 meals/ day)	B, L, D, and 3 smaller snacks in between B and L 12 weeks per regiment and then crossover to other regiment for 12 weeks Caloric restriction of 500kcal/day 50–55% CHO, 20–25% PRO, <30% FAT ($\leq 7\%$ SFAs, <200 mg/day of Chol), and 30–40 g/day of fibers	BW (signif.) -2.3kg in A6 -3.7kg in B2 HbA1c -0.23% in A6 -0.25% in B2 Fasting plasma Glu (mmol/L) -0.47 in A4 -0.78 in B2 Fasting immunoreactive Ins (pmol/L) -0.69 in A6 -0.75 in B2 Ins secretion at reference level (pmol min ⁻¹ m ⁻²) +22.9 in A6 +20 in B2 Glu sensitivity (pmol min ⁻¹ m ⁻² mmol ⁻¹ L ⁻¹) +5.8 in A6

						+5.9 in B2 TG (mmol/L) -0.28 in A6 -0.17 in B2 (all above changes per group were significant)
Arnold, et al., 1997 [182]	T2D or IGT 46-70 29.9±4.2	8 weeks Randomized, crossover study	13	3 meal regimes 9 meal regimes	Isoenergetic diets consisting of 3 or 9 meals/ day 4 weeks with 3meals/ day; Daily E needs: 25% at B, 25% at L, ~50% at D, and ~150 kcal at a snack 4 weeks with 9meals/ day; Daily E needs: 8.3% at early morning, 8.3% at B, 8.3% at mid-morning, 8.3% at L, 8.3% at mid-afternoon, 8.3% at late-afternoon, 8.3% at D, 16.6% at mid-evening, and 16.6% at late evening; Meals were 1-2hrs apart	Glu (mmol/L) +2% with 3 meals +4% with 9 meals Ins (µU/ml) +1% with 3 meals -2% with 9 meals Total Chol (mmol/L) +3.5% with 3 and with 9 meals TG (mmol/L) -13.5% with 3 and with 9 meals ApoB (mg/dL) +12% with 3 meals 17% with 9 meals
Salehi, et al., 2014 [184]	T2D 35-65 n/a	3 months RCT	66	6-meal group (6M) Control group (5 meals – usual pattern)	Weight loss diets (-300kcal/day) 6 isocaloric meals 3 large meals and 2 small snacks (Ctrl) 56% CHO, 16% PRO and 28% FAT	↓↓ BMI in 6M ↓ BMI in usual pattern ↓↓ HbA1c in 6M ↓↓ Ins and 2h-ppd Glu in 6M ↓↓ Ins in usual pattern

						no sign. differences in fasting Glu, fasting Ins, and 2h-ppd serum Glu in both groups
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• **Effect of the Distribution of Energy and Macronutrients in a day on Glycaemia**

Pearce, <i>et al.</i> , 2008 [34]	T2D 61.3±10 34.7±9	3 days Randomized crossover study	23	CARB-E CARB-B CARB-L CARB-D	Even CHO distribution is all meals/day ~70g CHO CHO mainly in B (~125g) CHO mainly in L (~125g) CHO mainly in D (~125g) 40% CHO, 34% PRO, 26% FAT	Glucose max (mmol/L): 14.2 ± 1.0 CARB-L 14.5±0.9 CARB-E 14.6±0.8 CARB-D 16.5±0.8 CARB-B Glu AUC ₂₀ (mmol/L•20 h): 10049±718 CARB-L 10493±706 CARB-E 10717±638 CARB-D 10603±642 CARB-B small but no sig. difference in fasting blood Glu
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2015 [157]	T2D 57.8±4.7 28.1±2.9	5 mo, 14 exp. days Randomized open-label crossover- within- subject clinical trial	18	Bdiet (HE breakfast) Ddiet (HE diner)	<u>Bdiet</u> : B – 2946 kJ, 31% PRO, 47% CHO, 22% FAT L – 2523 kJ, 27% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT D – 858 kJ, 43% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT <u>Ddiet</u> : B – 858 kJ, 43% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT L – 2523 kJ, 27% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT D – 2946 kJ, 31% PRO, 47% CHO, 22% FAT	-20% daily AUC _{Glu} for Bdiet -24% AUC _{Glu} in Bdiet after B Faster plasma Glu level decrease after B +11% AUC _{Ins} in Bdiet after B +12% Ins peak after B in Bdiet Faster Ins peak (60mins) after B in Bdiet -21-25% AUC _{Glu} in Bdiet after L

					<p>6276±105 kJ 31% PRO 46% CHO 23% FAT</p> <p>B at 08:00h L at 13:00h D at 19:00h</p>	<p>+23% AUC_{Ins} in Bdiet after L</p> <p>50% higher, and more rapid early prandial Ins in Bdiet after L</p>
Imai, et al., 2018 [165]	T2D 67.4±9.4 23.5±3.1	4 days Randomized, crossover clinical trial	17	<p>Group 1: Day 2 snack at 12:30h and day 3 snack at 15:30h</p> <p>Group 2: Day 2 snack at 15:30h and day 3 snack at 12:30h</p>	<p>Diet: Same meals in the 2 groups with B at 07:00 h, L at 12:00 h, D at 19:00h and snack at either 12:30h (just after lunch – early) or at 15:30h (mid-afternoon- late)</p>	<p>MAGE (mmol/L) 6.90±0.69 with early snack 5.19±0.48 with late snack</p> <p>iAUC (mmol/L per min⁻¹) 1030±180 with early snack 701±97 with late snack</p> <p>Time of snack did not affect the mean Glu level</p>
Kessler, et al., 2017 [166]	NGT and IGT 45.9±2.5 27.1±0.8	8 weeks Crossover trial	29	<p>HC/HF HF/HC</p>	<p>Isocaloric diets, with energy intake equally distributed in the day</p> <p>HC/HF for 4weeks: CHO-rich meals until 13:30h, and FAT-rich meals 16:30h-22:00h</p> <p>HF/HC for 4 weeks: FAT-rich meals until 13:30h, and CHO-rich meals 16:30h-22:00h</p>	<p>In subjects with impaired Glu tolerance and fasting Glu:</p> <p>Fasting Glucose -11.4% in HC/HF -9.6% in HF/HC</p> <p>Fasting Insulin -21.9% in HC/HF -27.1% in HF/HC</p> <p>Fasting C-peptide -42.6% in HC/HF -50.6% in HF/HC</p>

						<p>HOMA-IR -33.8% in HC/HF -34.7% in HF/HC</p> <p>Fasting GLP-1 -45% in HC/HF -13.3% in HF/HC</p> <p>Whole day Glu +7.9% in HF/HC vs HC/HF</p>
Gibbs, et al., 2014 [167]	Healthy 25.5±8.8 21.9±1.7	4 exp. days Randomized, crossover study	10	Low GI meals (LG) High GI meals (HG)	LG: GI~37 HG: GI~73 LG and HG were consumed at (am) 8:00h and (pm) 20:00h	<p>Glu peak (mmol/L) 7.8±0.4 with LG & HG am 8.3±0.2 with LG pm 9.54±0.4 with HG pm</p> <p>Glu 2h-ppd (mmol/L) Glu peak (mmol/L) 4.85±0.2 with LG & HG am 6.42±0.4 with LG & HG am</p> <p>no sig. differences in iAUC_{Glu} but a trend for ↓ iAUC_{Glu} with am meals</p> <p>no sig. differences in iAUC_{Ins}</p>

Abbreviations: IGT: impaired glucose tolerance; T2D: type 2 diabetes; NGT: normal glucose tolerance; B: Breakfast; L: Lunch; D: Dinner; E: total energy intake; ppd: postprandial; GI: Glycemic Index, Glu: Glucose, Ins: Insulin, AUC: Area Under the Curve, iAUC: incremental area under the curve; CHO: carbohydrates; PRO: proteins; FAT: fats; M: meals; FPG: fasting plasma glucose; BW: body weight; RCT: randomized controlled clinical trial; HC: high carbohydrate; HF: igh fat; HOMA: homeostatic model assessment for insulin